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3 **On the evaluation of the suitability of the materials**
4 **used to 3D print holographic acoustic lenses to correct**
5 **transcranial focused ultrasound aberrations**

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19 **Abstract:** The correction of transcranial focused ultrasound aberrations is a relevant topic for
20 enhancing various non-invasive medical treatments. Nowadays, the most widely accepted method to
21 improve focusing is the emission through multi-element phased arrays; however, a new disruptive
22 technology, based on 3D printed holographic acoustic lenses, has recently been proposed overcoming
23 the spatial limitations of phased arrays due to the submillimetric precision of the latest generation of
24 3D printers. This work aims to optimize this recent solution; particularly, the preferred acoustic
25 properties of the polymers used for printing the lens are systematically analyzed, paying special
26 attention to the effect of p-wave speed and its relationship to the achievable voxel size of 3D printers.
27 Results from simulations and experiments clearly show that there are optimal ranges for lens
28 thickness and p-wave speed, fairly independent of the emitted frequency, the transducer aperture, or
29 the transducer-target distance, given a particular voxel size.

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33 **Keywords:** 3D printed lenses, focused ultrasound, transcranial ultrasound, single-element transducer,
34 transcranial therapy. Polymers

1. Introduction

Holography is a technique to reconstruct wave fields from the previous recording of their complete amplitude and phase information. Optical holograms have been widely developed in many scientific, technological and even artistic applications; however acoustic holograms have been notably less applied to interest cases. Most acoustic holographic techniques are based on phased arrays with a large number of transducers [1, 2], requiring sophisticated electronic circuits highly sensitive to calibration inaccuracies. However, new advances in metamaterials and the design capabilities of the state of art 3D printers allow the development of passive structures capable of shaping complicated acoustic fields [3-9].

An ambit in which precise holographic reconstruction of acoustic fields is gaining importance in recent years is in focused ultrasound for medical applications (FUS), mainly in non-invasive treatments where the ultrasound propagates through tissues with very different acoustic impedances, as is the case of transcranial propagation [8-16]. The first successful transcranial ablation of animal brain tissue was achieved by Fry and Goss in 1980 [16], since then, many clinical procedures have been improved by applying transcranial focused ultrasound. Treatment of brain tumours [17, 18], Alzheimer's disease [19] or Parkinson's disease [20] can be enhanced by this technique. The administration of FUS allows a local transient opening of the blood-brain barrier (BBB) [13-21] improving the delivery of pharmacological substances such as anticancer therapeutic drugs [22], neurotrophic factors [23], adeno-associated viruses [24, 25], and neural stem cells [12].

The success of these medical treatments is linked to an adequate reduction of skull-induced aberrations to achieve a precise ultrasound focusing. Early approaches included ultrasonic therapy after craniotomy [26] or less aggressive techniques such as the application of FUS without correction of aberrations, but radiating from regular and flat areas of the skull [27]. More recent approaches mainly rely on actively shaping the wavefront to correct bone-induced aberrations through the use of holographic lenses or multi-element transducer arrays whose phase can be adjusted individually. The required phase registration is performed by inverse propagation, measured or simulated, from target to transducer. Initially, phase patterns were assessed by physically placing a reference transducer inside the brain at target location [28, 29]; nowadays, the technique is absolutely non-invasive as acceptable phase patterns can be obtained by numerical simulation [14, 30-31].

The research aiming to improve the technique can be based both on (i) a better recording of the phase -associated with the knowledge of the physical variables of each element of volume scanned by medical imaging and with the numerical methods applied- and on (ii) a better reconstruction of the recorded field. In this work we are going to address the second issue. In fact, the aberration correction by multi-element phased arrays is subjected to technological limitations associated with the size and number of singular elements that can be implemented in the phased arrays. These limitations can be overcome by shaping the wavefront using high transparency 3D printed refractive ultrasound lenses [6, 8]. In fact, the work published by Maimbourg et al. [6] demonstrates that the spatial resolution, associated with the voxel size achieved by the latest generation of 3D printers, improves dramatically the space resolution of phased arrays, leading to better focusing. Therefore, in addition to the actual race towards creating arrays with an ever-increasing number of elements, the holographic acoustic lens approach emerge as a promising technology allowing submillimetric phase correction with limited cost.

In this work, assuming the relevance that 3D holographic lenses can take for transcranial FUS treatments in the near future, we aim to systematically evaluate the physical properties that the polymers used in their elaboration must have in order to reconstruct the desired acoustic field in an optimal way. There are trivial aspects, as that the lens must have maximum transparency, however, other aspects, such as those relating to the shape of the lens and the sound speed in the polymer- intimately linked to each other- require a more detailed quantitative study. In fact, in previous works, polymers with lower [6] or higher [8,9] than water wave speeds have been indistinctly used to build the lenses; without explicitly expressing a suitability criterion. In both slow and fast materials their p-wave speeds condition the thickness and shape of the lenses, and there are important aspects of lens quality associated with shape such as (i) the validity of the theoretical approach that assumes the hypothesis of ideally thin lenses, or (ii) the effect of voxel size on the printed lens, since the relative

1 discretization of the lens is more abrupt in thin lenses. In order to give a quantitative response, or at
 2 least a guide to solve these questions, a series of numerical simulations and a validation experiment
 3 are proposed, the results of which are discussed and justified.

6 2. Materials and Methods

8 2.1. Physical parameters obtained from computerized tomographies

10 Numerical simulations were conducted using the data acquired by computerized tomography
 11 (CT) of a human head (freely available at repository cancerimagingarchive.net for scientific purposes)
 12 with an interslice spacing of 0.63 mm and an in-plane spatial resolution of 0.49 mm. 3D linear
 13 interpolation of the radiodensity known at each node of this parallelepiped mesh is performed to
 14 obtain a denser cubic simulation grid with a spatial step, $h = 0.244$ mm. Different excitation
 15 frequencies are applied in simulations, being the highest 760 kHz, so a ratio $\lambda/h > 8$ at water is ensured,
 16 which introduces acceptable numerical phase error in the simulations[32].

17 The elastodynamic damped equations for isotropic solids are applied at the whole computational
 18 domain, since the dynamics of the wave propagation in fluids can be defined as a particular case of
 19 solid with null shear modulus G . A set of four independent parameters must be known at each
 20 computational node, being these (i) the density in equilibrium ρ , (ii) the p-wave speed c , (iii) the
 21 attenuation coefficient α , and (iv) the Poisson's ratio, ν . The two first parameters are obtained by
 22 means of the linear interpolations [6]

$$23 \quad c(x, y, z) = c_{water} + (c_{bone} - c_{water}) \frac{HU(x, y, z) - HU_{min}}{HU_{max} - HU_{min}} \quad (1)$$

$$24 \quad \rho(x, y, z) = \rho_{water} + (\rho_{bone} - \rho_{water}) \frac{HU(x, y, z) - HU_{min}}{HU_{max} - HU_{min}} \quad (2)$$

25 where HU is the radiodensity in Hounsfield units, ρ_{water} and c_{water} are respectively the density and
 26 p-wave speed of water at 21°C, and ρ_{bone} and c_{bone} are respectively the density and p-wave speed of
 27 cortical bone at that temperature. Radiodensity values out of the interval 0 to 2400 HU were set
 28 respectively to these saturation values expected for water and cortical bone [33]. In accordance with
 29 bibliography [6, 34, 35, 36] the values considered for water and cortical bone are

$$30 \quad c_{bone} = 3100 \text{ m/s}, \quad \rho_{bone} = 1900 \text{ kg/m}^3, \quad c_{water} = 1485 \text{ m/s}, \quad \rho_{water} = 10^3 \text{ kg/m}^3.$$

31 Since the dependence of radiodensity on attenuation coefficient and Poisson's ratio has not been
 32 investigated in depth, we have applied a simplified approach for these parameters, obtaining an
 33 average value at each domain. For the attenuation coefficients at 760 kHz we have taken $\alpha_{brain} = 2$ Np/m,
 34 and $\alpha_{skull} = 60$ Np/m. [8, 34, 37-38], and Poisson's ratio at the skull has been defined as uniform with a
 35 value $\nu_{skull} = 0.316$ to achieve a constant relation between p-wave and s-wave speeds, $c_p/c_s = 27/14$, as
 36 proposed by Hughes et al. [39].

38 2.2. Governing equations and numerical model

40 A linear centered elastodynamic FDTD method has been developed by the authors in Matlab
 41 (The MathWorks, Inc. Massachusetts. USA). The governing equations for both fluid and isotropic
 42 solid media, are [8]:

$$43 \quad \frac{\partial \tau_{ij}}{\partial t} = (M - 2G) \delta_{ij} (\nabla \cdot \vec{u}) + G \left(\frac{\partial u_i}{\partial x_j} + \frac{\partial u_j}{\partial x_i} \right) \quad (3)$$

$$44 \quad \rho \frac{\partial u_i}{\partial t} + \sigma \cdot u_i = \sum_j \frac{\partial \tau_{ij}}{\partial x_j} \quad (4)$$

45 where u is the particle velocity, τ_{ij} are the components of the stress tensor, δ_{ij} is the Kronecker
 46 delta, ρ is the density in equilibrium, M and G are respectively the p-wave and the shear moduli, and
 47 σ is an artificial absorption parameter generating an exponential space dependent attenuation in

1 isotropic media. The value of σ is implemented to obtain the proper attenuation coefficient, for both
 2 solid and fluid media, attending to the relation proposed by Ferri et al [8]

$$3 \quad \sigma = \rho \sqrt{\left(\omega + \frac{2c^2 \alpha^2}{\omega} \right)^2 - \omega^2}, \quad (5)$$

4 where ω is the angular frequency, c the p-wave speed and α , in Nepers per meter, is the
 5 absorption at the media. Shear modulus, G , is obtained from its known relation with Poisson's rate
 6 and p-wave modulus at solid media, and forced to zero in fluid domain.

7 Equations 3 and 4 are valid for both solid and fluid media. At liquid media, the null value of the
 8 shear modulus G leads to a null value of the tangential stresses and to an equal value of the three axial
 9 stresses at each point, equivalent to the fluid pressure with opposite sign. The parameter M represents
 10 respectively the p-wave modulus at solid domain and the bulk modulus at fluid; and it is obtained at
 11 any point as

$$12 \quad M = \rho c^2 \quad (6)$$

13 The excitation signal, for both time forward and time reversal simulations, consists of a harmonic
 14 pressure excitation enveloped by a half Hanning window during the first n cycles, with $n = 8$.
 15 Excitation pressure is implemented in complex form, in order to facilitate the phase computation at
 16 the holographic registration surface, as

$$17 \quad \tau_{11} = \tau_{22} = \tau_{33} = -p_o \sin^2 \left(\frac{\omega}{4n} \min \left(t, \frac{2n\pi}{\omega} \right) \right) (\cos(\omega t) + j \sin(\omega t)). \quad (7)$$

18 The time step Δt is adjusted to a 0.075 Courant–Friedrichs–Lewy (CFL) condition at water that
 19 ensures stability at the fastest evaluated holographic lens that is four times faster than water being
 20 also faster than cortical bone. The definition of a CFL linked to the water, instead of dependent on the
 21 fastest media as usual, attends to the fact that the numerical isotropy of the wave speed is CFL
 22 dependent [40]. Its oversized value intends to avoid favouring propagation in some lenses over others,
 23 as it is far from the optimum in all cases.

24

25 **Figure 1.** Schematic sagittal cross section of the skull, representing the positions of
 26 target points and registration surfaces considered in numerical simulations.
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2.3. Holographic phase pattern registration

The lens shape is derived from the phase pattern obtained by simulation at the holographic registration surface, concentric to the surface where the transducer must be placed, at a distance equivalent to the nominal lens thickness (Figure 1). Properly, the holographic registration surface is a Cartesian discretized spherical or plane surface where the phase is obtained from the value of the pressure in complex form known at the Cartesian nodes of the computational grid. This pressure field is simulated by the time reversal propagation of a single frequency wave emitted at the target point. At the stationary state, achieved several periods after the wave reaches the registration surface, the numerically computed phase shift between any two points of the computational domain remains remarkably constant. Phases calculated at the holographic registration surface are not subjected to a process of unwrapping, as recommended in previous works [6, 8], since this work is focused in evaluating holographic Fresnel lenses capable of a maximum phase shift of 2π . Instead, we just add an arbitrary value to the phase pattern to reduce the region of the lens affected by an abrupt 2π phase shift

2.4. Numerical design of holographic lens

The thickness at each point of the lens defined in spherical coordinates, $h(\theta, \varphi)$ is obtained by linear interpolation from the phase $\beta(\theta, \varphi)$ computed at the holographic registration surface, as follows

$$h(\theta, \varphi) = \frac{\beta(\theta, \varphi)}{2\pi} d \quad \text{or} \quad h(\theta, \varphi) = \frac{2\pi - \beta(\theta, \varphi)}{2\pi} d \quad (8)$$

where the first expression is used for lenses made with materials with wave speed smaller than water and the second for fast lenses, and where d is the nominal lens thickness obtained for both fast and slow lenses, as a function of its relative speed ($c_{rel} = c_{p_lens} / c_{water}$), as

$$d = \left| \frac{c_{rel}}{c_{rel} - 1} \right| \lambda_{water} \quad (9)$$

where, λ_{water} is the wavelength of the surrounding media (generally water) and the relative speed is obtained from the p-wave speed of the lens. The phases, $\beta(\theta, \varphi)$, required to obtain the thickness pattern of the lens, $h(\theta, \varphi)$, are computed after interpolating the phases, $\beta(x, y, z)$, at the Cartesian holographic registration surface to the closest points of a mesh defined in spherical coordinates centered at the transducer focus. If 3D lenses are implemented in simulations, their shapes are linearly interpolated back to Cartesian domain

Linear interpolation proposed in equation 8 is accurate if no inner reflections in both surfaces of the lens are considered, i.e if the acoustic impedance of the lens is reasonably similar to the acoustic impedance of the surrounding media (water). If this hypothesis of total transmission is not acceptable, the thickness of the lens should be obtained applying the Fabry-Pérot approach, as proposed by Jimenez-Gambín et al [9]. This approach attends to an implicit expression that should be solved numerically for each value of $\beta(\theta, \varphi)$. The relevance of the systematic error assumed by applying the explicit linear interpolation is discussed in later sections.

2.5. Experimental equipment and materials

The acoustical lens employed at the validation experiment was manufactured by stereolithographic 3D-printing techniques (Forms 2, Formlabs Inc., USA) using a photopolymer resin (Grey Standard Form 2, Formlabs Inc., USA) with a resolution of 100 μm , as shown in Figure 2(a). The material was post-cured after 3D printing process with a 1.25 mW/cm² of 405 nm LED light for 30 minutes at 60 °C. The acoustical properties of the material were obtained experimentally using a pulse-echo technique in a test cylinder with a height of 30 mm and radius 25 mm, resulting in a measured sound speed of $c_p = 2440.7$ m/s and a density of $\rho = 1162.0$ kg/m³; as listed in Table 1 where data of a set of 3D printable polymers are presented [41-45].

The rest of devices applied consist of a single-element piezoelectric transducer (PZT26 Ferroperm Piezoceramics, Denmark), a signal generator (PXI5412, National Instruments, USA) amplified by a linear RF amplifier (1040L, ENI, Rochester, NY), a needle hydrophone (HNR-500, Onda) calibrated from 1 MHz to 20 MHz, a digitizer (PXI5620, National Instruments, USA) and a precision 3D micro-positioning system (OWIS GmbH, Germany) All the signal generation and acquisition processes were based on a NI8176 National Instruments PXI-Technology controller, which also controlled the micro-positioning system.

Material	Tech.	Dens. (g/cm ³)	Young (MPa)	M (MPa)	ν	c (m/s)	c_{rel}	z_{rel}	τ	d (λ)	d (voxel)
Somos®											
PerFORM	SLA	1,61	10500	19830	0,32	3510	2,36	3,81	0,66	1,73	14
Polyamida	FDM	1,36	5000	10710	0,4	2810	1,89	2,57	0,81	2,12	17
Standard Grey®	SLA	1,16	3000	6970	0,41	2440	1,65	1,92	0,9	2,54	20
PEEK	FDM	1,32	3600	7710	0,4	2420	1,63	2,15	0,87	2,59	21
PPS	FDM	1,63	4000	8570	0,4	2290	1,54	2,52	0,81	2,84	23
PEI	FDM	1,27	3200	6380	0,39	2240	1,51	1,92	0,9	2,96	24
VERO® Clear	SLA	1,17	3000	4810	0,35	2030	1,37	1,6	0,95	3,73	30
ABS	FDM	1,09	2500	4420	0,37	2010	1,36	1,48	0,96	3,81	30
PSU	FDM	1,25	2610	4620	0,37	1920	1,29	1,62	0,94	4,4	35
PLA	FDM	1,26	2600	4170	0,35	1820	1,23	1,54	0,95	5,44	44
Silicone	Mold	0,98	150	1320	0,48	1160	0,78	0,77	0,98	3,56	28
FEP	DLP	2,17	500	1900	0,45	930	0,63	1,37	0,98	1,7	14
TPU	FDM	1,1	500	440	0,48	630	0,43	0,47	0,87	0,74	6

Table 1. Acoustical data of a series of 3D printable polymers, assuming for water $c=1485m/s$ and $z=1485krayl$. τ represents acoustic transmission on a single layer lens/water, nominal thickness, d , is obtained assuming a frequency of 760kHz and a voxel size of 0.244mm.

Figure 2. (a) Photograph of the flat-lens manufactured by stereolithographic 3D-printing technique using a photopolymer. (b) Scheme of the setup and equipment used for the experiments in water tank.

2.6. Sources of errors in the printed lenses

The main causes of error in the correction of the aberration, assuming a perfect application of the technique (i.e., disregarding any error associated with the position and orientation of the lens once printed), are described here. Even supposing an exact knowledge of the physical parameters at each point of the brain and skull and a set of equations accurately describing the dynamics of the wave, there would be two inevitable sources of error affecting the computational modelling of the lens: those relative to (i) the discretization of the domain and (ii) the theoretical simplifications assumed in the design of the lens shape starting from the registered hologram.

1 Regarding domain discretization, given the dependence between the accuracy of any numerical
 2 method and its computational cost, the only way to eventually achieve a null error would be with an
 3 infinite computational cost [46]. On the other hand, obtaining the shape of the lens from the registered
 4 hologram presents several difficulties. In the definition of the lens thickness as a function of the phase
 5 pattern recorded at the holographic surface -either by means of the Fabry-Pérot resonator approach [9]
 6 or by means of the proposed linear interpolation- the hypothesis of an idealized propagation of each
 7 ray in radial direction (transducer-center) from the transducer to the holographic surface is being
 8 assumed. This assumption is incorrect, since the ray changes direction at the periphery of the lens and
 9 not at the holographic surface; however, the thinner the lens, the truer it will be. The hypothesis
 10 assumed here of a linear relationship between the registered phase and lens thickness -rather than
 11 applying a more accurate model- is a second cause of error associated with this item.

12 In addition to the two aforementioned causes of error, exclusively associated with the numerical
 13 simulation that concludes obtaining the CAD model of the lens as an STL file, the process of
 14 generating a physical lens starting from the CAD model is affected by three new error sources: (i)
 15 inaccuracy of shape, (ii) discretization of the shape, and (iii) imprecision in the physical parameters
 16 that affect wave propagation, such as density, Young's modulus, Poisson's ratio, or acoustic
 17 absorption associated with the presence of anisotropy, porosity, heterogeneity, etc, related with the
 18 printing process. The inaccuracy of shape will be considered negligible in this study, since updated 3D
 19 printers can generate decimeter objects with inaccuracies of less than one tenth of a millimeter. As for
 20 the discretization of the shape of the lens, the dimensions of the elementary volume cell (voxel)
 21 depend on the 3D printing method (FDM, SLA, etc.) and the material used. Furthermore, given that
 22 3D printing is a booming sector, the minimum voxel size is continuously being reduced. For the
 23 present study we have accepted a cubic voxel with a side of 0.244 mm, since it is a reasonable value
 24 that matches with the grid element used in numerical calculations. Regarding the third cause of error,
 25 it should be noted that the anisotropy of the printing process itself (which is carried out in layers) can
 26 lead to large anisotropies in the value of the propagation speed, which is the most relevant parameter
 27 for the proper performance of these lenses. In this sense, it can be highlighted that if resins with fibers
 28 are used in FDM printing, we can find large anisotropies, such as compressibility modules of
 29 respective values $B_x = 10$ GPa and $B_{yz} = 1,12$ GPa [41]. In general, SLA printing with subsequent curing
 30 using fiberless resins is the process that guarantees greater isotropy, although a certain degree of
 31 anisotropy or heterogeneity in the physical values of the printed lens can never be neglected [42-45].

32 Summarizing, five sources of error have been considered: discretization of the numerical domain,
 33 validity of the theoretical approach, inaccuracy in the form of the printed physical lens, discretization
 34 of the printed lens and imprecision in the relative p-wave speed of the printed lens. Between these, the
 35 inaccuracy in the form has been neglected and the size of the voxel associated with the printing
 36 process has been set to the size of the cell used for the numerical calculations. Thus three sources of
 37 error will be studied: spatial discretization, imprecision on the polymer p-wave speed and validity of
 38 the theoretical approach.

39 The effect associated with the imprecision in the relative speed of the printed lenses, accepted
 40 their isotropy, can be approached as follows. The maximum phase shift produced by a lens with a
 41 nominal thickness, d , being c_{rel} the ratio between the p-wave speeds of the lens and the medium, is
 42 written

$$43 \quad \beta = \left| \frac{2\pi}{\lambda_{water}} - \frac{2\pi}{c_{rel} \lambda_{water}} \right| d \quad (10)$$

44
 45 If the lens is made with a negligible error in its dimensions, the absolute uncertainty of the phase
 46 shift, $\mathcal{E}(\beta)$, associated exclusively with the imprecision of the relative speed is obtained as follows
 47

$$48 \quad \mathcal{E}(\beta) = \frac{2\pi}{c_{rel}^2 \lambda_{water}} d \cdot \mathcal{E}(c_{rel}) \quad (11)$$

49 and knowing the value of the nominal thickness according to equation 9, the phase error as a
 50 function of the relative error of the relative velocity, $\mathcal{E}_r(c_{rel})$, can be expressed as

$$\varepsilon(\beta) = \left| \frac{2\pi}{c_{rel} - 1} \right| \varepsilon_r(c_{rel}) \quad (12)$$

Regarding the effect on the phase shift associated to the spatial discretization of the lens, we can state that the maximum error of the phase shift, $\varepsilon'(\beta)$, associated with the size of the voxel is written

$$\varepsilon'(\beta) = \left| \frac{2\pi}{n_d} \right| \quad (13)$$

Where n_d represents the number of voxels associated with the nominal lens thickness. Thus, knowing the nominal thickness according to equation 9 and being n_λ the number of voxels per wavelength in water, it is trivial to obtain

$$n_d = \left| \frac{c_{rel}}{c_{rel} - 1} \right| n_\lambda, \quad (14)$$

and combining the above equations 13, and 14 we get

$$\varepsilon'(\beta) = \left| \frac{c_{rel} - 1}{c_{rel}} \right| \frac{2\pi}{n_\lambda}, \quad (15)$$

For a better understanding of the implications of the expressions 12 and 15 the Figure 3 is attached. There can be appreciated that, if polymer p-wave speeds are close to that of water, the error associated with relative speed shoots towards infinity, whereas that associated with discretization tends to zero. It can be seen that the curves are asymmetrical, obtaining for both errors a more favourable trend in the high speeds zone.

Figure 3. Analytical estimation of the uncertainties in the phase recreated by the 3D lens at the holographic surface associated with the discretization of the domain expressed in voxels per water wavelength, vpw_{water} (dashed), with the acoustic impedance of the lens when the definition of the thickness is approached by linear interpolation (dotted) and with possible differences between simulated and real values of lens p-wave speed (continuous).

1 The last error factor considered is the validity of the theoretical approach itself that is affected by
2 an accidental and a systematic error. The accidental error is associated with the difference between the
3 actual ray path and the idealized path that tends to coincide in very thin lenses. This accidental error
4 is difficult to quantify, and will be evaluated through a series of numerical simulations. In addition, a
5 systematic error, associated with the estimation of the thickness of the lens by means of a simple linear
6 interpolation and not by means of a more accurate model such as the Fabry-Pérot resonator [9], is
7 introduced. The reasons for using the linear hypothesis in this work are simple: First, (i) both models
8 converge when the impedances of water and lens are equal and the total transparency is reached,
9 (condition that has been applied in the set of numerical simulations evaluated), and second (ii) to
10 apply the Fabry-Pérot resonator model, the acoustic impedances of the transducer, of the backing and
11 of the coupling agent must be known. This would enforce us to play with many input variables with a
12 minor effect on the quality of the approach, and therefore we have dismissed this variability for the
13 study. The maximum value of the systematic error in the phase associated with the assumption of the
14 linear approach is represented in Figure 3. This error has been calculated as the worst in the whole
15 phase interval $[0, 2\pi)$ in the absence of coupling between transducer and lens by comparing the linear
16 model with a Fabry-Pérot resonator.

17 Concluding, it can be stated that while the p-wave speed of each polymer affects lens shape and
18 therefore the validity of the thin lens hypothesis, its acoustic impedance is not a direct cause of error in
19 the phase generated at the registration surface. However, if this impedance is very different from that
20 of water, transmission is decreased what is energetically inefficient. No study on optimal impedance
21 has been proposed, therefore, as it is simple to conclude that the ideal lens would have an impedance
22 equal to that of water.

23 24 **3. Experiments and simulations**

25
26 In order to determine the suitability of the polymers attending to their p-wave speed, a set of
27 numerical simulations and a validation experiments are performed whose details are described here.
28 The obtained results are presented and discussed in later sections.

29 30 *3.1. Numerical Simulations*

31
32 The simulations are carried out with or without skull interposed between transducer and target,
33 which are placed at different points (P1, P2, P3) always between the spherical transducer and its
34 geometrical center (Fig. 1). At each of these points and for each emitted frequency, we assume the
35 same protocol: First of all, the phase pattern is recorded (by means of time reversal simulation from
36 target to transducer) on the holographic recording surface, both with and without interposed skull.
37 Then, in order to determine the characteristics of the ideal focus, the “gold standard emission”, which
38 consists on emitting from the registration surface affected by the phase pattern recorded without skull,
39 is simulated. Next, a series of six lenses for six different speeds slower than water and another series
40 of six lenses for six speeds faster than water are numerically generated from both the phase patterns
41 recorded with or without skull. In the graphs and for the sake of brevity, we name concave or convex
42 lenses the lenses produced respectively with fast or slow materials, since all the target points
43 evaluated are located between the lens and its geometric center. The p-wave speeds evaluated ranges
44 from one fourth to four times the wave speed of water.

45 Once calculated the lens at each configuration (i.e. at each point, at each frequency, with or
46 without skull) and for each p-wave speed of the lens polymer, the numerical medium is modified by
47 adding each Cartesian model of the acoustic lens placed in the correct position to generate the
48 holographic pattern. Then, the time forward emission is simulated from the spherical transducer,
49 emitting with uniform initial phase and amplitude, and placed concentric to the phase registration
50 surface at a distance from it equivalent to the value of the nominal lens thickness. A backing with the
51 same acoustic properties of the lens is added to avoid the numerical issues related with placing the
52 emitting nodes at a boundary.

53 The density of each simulated lens is established in accordance to its p-wave speed in order to set
54 a unit normalised impedance for each polymer. Therefore, the simultaneous evaluation of velocity and

1 impedance effects is avoided, but the properties of the simulated polymers could not correspond to
2 any physical material.

3 For each of these simulations, the quality of the -3 dB and -6 dB focus beams is evaluated
4 attending to seven quantitative indicators described below. The particular values used in the
5 simulation series are the following: the p-wave speeds of the fast lenses are respectively 4, 2.5, 1.75,
6 1.5, 1.375 and 1.3 times the speed of water, whereas the p-wave speeds of the slow lenses are obtained
7 dividing the speed of water by the same series of numbers; the spherical transducers have a radius of
8 59 mm and an aperture of 64mm for configuration P3, and 30mm for P1 and P2 and. Figure 1 shows
9 the target points whose respective distances to the holographic surface are 24.2 mm 13.8 mm and 30
10 mm. In short, there are 96 time forward simulations for the small aperture lens (two types of lens, two
11 frequencies, with and without skull, two positions, and six speeds) and 13 simulations for the lens of
12 larger aperture.

13 3.2. Quantitative focusing indicators

14 To assess the quality of the focal spot achieved by each kind of material we calculate seven
15 quantitative indicators as described by Ferri et al. [8] for both -3 dB and -6 dB focal beams. These
16 indicators evaluate for each focal beam (i) its longitudinal and transverse deviations from the target
17 point (z, R) , (ii) its transverse an total gyradii (k_R, k) , (iii) orientation, $\Delta\phi$, (iv) focal volume, V , and (v)
18 energetic overlapping with the ideal focus, $I_i(\%)$.

19 3.3. Experiments

20 A validation of the simulation was performed by measuring the acoustical field of a 3D printed
21 test lens in the ultrasonic regime. The experiments were done inside a 1 x 0.75 x 0.5 m degassed-
22 distilled water tank at 21° C, as shown in Figure 2(b). The lens was excited using a custom-made
23 ultrasonic source composed of single-element piezoelectric transducer mounted in a custom designed
24 stainless-steel housing with a diameter $2a = 50$ mm. The transducer was driven with a 50 cycles
25 sinusoidal pulse burst at a frequency of $f = 1.112$ MHz. The pressure field was mapped by a 500- μ m
26 needle hydrophone. The hydrophone signals were digitized at a sampling rate of 64 MHz averaged 50
27 times to increase the signal to noise ratio. A precision 3D micro-positioning system was used to move
28 the hydrophone in three orthogonal directions with an accuracy of 10 μ m. Scanned area covered from
29 -3 mm to 3 mm in the x and y axis, and from 10 to 35 mm in the z axis, using a step of 0.1 mm in all
30 directions. Temperature measurements were performed throughout the whole process to ensure no
31 temperature changes of 1° C.

32 4. Results

33 This section presents the results of the set of simulations evaluated and the validation experiment
34 carried out. Numerical parameterization of the focusing at each configuration simulated has been
35 performed for both -3dB and -6dB beams, however, given the similarity of the results obtained; only
36 the indicators obtained at -6dB will be presented.

37 4.1. Emission in water at 760 kHz

38 **Positional deviation of the focus:** The longitudinal focal point deviations of the -6 dB beam, for
39 the simulations performed with each of the lens evaluated, are shown in Figure 4(a). It can be seen
40 that the trends found in the deviation values are different for concave and convex lenses, but
41 somehow independent on the evaluated point. The obtained longitudinal deviations for the convex
42 lenses seem to present optimum values for nominal lens thickness between 10 and 20 voxels whereas,
43 for concave lenses at points P1 and P2, the results show that the thinner, the better. Concave lens at
44 point P3 exhibits an intermediate behaviour, with a flat trend between 10 and 15 voxels.

45 The transverse deviations found (Figure 4(b)) are negligible compared to the emitted wavelength
46 ($\lambda_{\text{water}} \approx 2$ mm at 760 kHz) and to the size of the voxel for all the configurations evaluated, showing a

1 maximum value of 60 μm which is less than one third of the computational internode distance. No
 2 trend can be analyzed as the calculated transverse deviations are simply showing an stochastic
 3 behaviour.

4
 5 **Figure 4.** Focusing quality indicators calculated by simulation in water with 760 kHz, at points P1, P2
 6 and P3, for concave (fast) and convex (slow) lenses. Indicators are: (a) Longitudinal and (b) transverse
 7 deviation, (c) transverse and (d) total gyradius, (e) beam volume and (f) energetic overlapping.

8
 9 **Gyradius:** The proper beam shape, considered similar to the shape of the reference beam, is
 10 evaluated using the transverse, k_R , and total, k , gyradii of the -6 dB focal beams (Figures 4(c-d)). The
 11 reference -6 dB beam obtained at P1 has the values $k_R = 0.63$ mm $k = 2.26$ mm, and at P2 the values are
 12 $k_R = 0.44$ mm $k = 1.23$ mm. Both transverse and total gyradii at the -6dB focal beams have certain
 13 similarities with those of the reference beam, at all the evaluated points and for concave and convex
 14 lenses. Particularly, and with the exception of a couple of cases of the total gyradius for convex lenses
 15 at both P1 and P2, the beams with interposed lenses are larger than the reference beam, as could be
 16 expected. Therefore, the smaller the gyradius the more accurate the beam. Then, we found that
 17 concave lenses –as in positional deviation- show its best results for nominal lens thickness between 10

1 and 20 voxels at both P1, P2 and P2; whereas convex lenses seems to present the best values with
2 lightly thicker lenses for P1. At P2, however, the transverse gyradius presents a clear trend with an
3 optimum between 10 and 20 voxels and the trend of the total gyradius behaves pretty like in P1.
4 Concave lens at P3 shows relatively flat trends but an optimum range between 10 and 20 voxels can
5 again be appreciated.

6 **Focal volume:** The focal volume is compared with that of the reference beam founding that
7 reference is always smaller with values 26.1mm³ for P1 and 6.8mm³ for P2. It is somehow obvious
8 that the focal volume is highly linked with the gyradii values, so the trends found in Figure 4(c-e)
9 present high similarities. As in gyradius, we find that for concave lenses at the three points the trends
10 signals clearly an optimum when the nominal lens thickness is between 10 and 20 voxels, and in
11 convex lenses the optimum for both P1 and P2 is found at slightly larger lens thickness

12 It is also remarkable that the most accurate values present a great similitude with the reference
13 beam, with differences as slight as 1% whereas the thickest or thinnest lenses presents values with
14 differences with the reference beam as large as 56%.

15 **Orientation** No plot of orientation is presented, as their average values in water are smaller than
16 0.009rad (0.5°). This indicator here only informs about numerical uncertainty as in the case of
17 transverse deviation.

18 **Energetic overlapping:** Figure 4(f) shows that the largest overlappings for -6db beams are
19 achieved at point P3 and P1 with concave lenses, with values as big as 89%. Concave lenses exhibit a
20 slight better behaviour than convex ones for both points P1 and P2, and P1 shows better overlapping
21 than P2 regardless the kind of lens. The trend at the five curves shows similarities with that observed
22 in previous parameters such as focal volume and gyradius. The best overlappings are found with lens
23 thickness between 10 and 20 voxels for all the cases with the only exception of convex lenses at
24 P1 where the optimum is found between 15 and 25 voxels.

26 4.2. Transcranial emission at 760 kHz

28 **Positional deviation of the focus:** In transcranial emission both longitudinal and transverse focal
29 point deviations (z and R) are relevant, and its values for the -6 dB beams are shown in Figure 5(a,b).
30 Transverse deviations obtained are relatively small compared to the emitted wavelength ($\lambda_{\text{water}} \approx 2\text{mm}$
31 at 760kHz) and to the size of the voxel in the evaluated cases, for each of the thicknesses, points and
32 types of lens. Their values smaller than 0,6mm in all the cases are notably smaller than the values of
33 the longitudinal deviation, that are smaller than 3 mm in all the cases.

34 Despite the small values found for transverse deviations the trends can be easily appreciated, and
35 are notably similar those found in previous indicators such as gyradius or focal volume in underwater
36 case. Again the smallest deviations for concave and convex lenses at the points P1 and P2 are obtained
37 in the interval between 10 and 20 voxels; point P3 exhibits an aggressive trend with a minimum
38 around 15 voxels. The smallest deviations at P1 are achieved by the concave lens and, at P2, by the
39 convex one.

40 For longitudinal deviation, there are some similitude between the trends obtained for the
41 underwater and the transcranial case. In transcranial case, trends are less explicit, but show again that
42 the optimum nominal thickness for the convex lens is found between 10 and 20 voxels at P1 and
43 bigger than 10 voxels at P2, whereas, for concave lenses, at points P1 and P2, it is found that the
44 thinner the better, and at point P3 the optimal interval is again between 10 and 20 voxels.

46 **Gyradius:** Transverse, k_R , and total, k , radii of gyration of the -6dB focal beams are shown at
47 Figure 5(c,d). A great concordance between the data at both plots can be highlighted for points P1 and
48 P2, since the trends of transverse gyradii are almost exactly proportional to those of the total gyradii
49 for any type of lens. On the contrary, point P3 shows transverse gyradii values notably larger than
50 expected. The values at the three points, for any type of gyradius at any simulation, are again slightly
51 bigger than the reference values, displayed at Figure 4(c,d). It is notable the similitude between the
52 results found with concave and convex lenses, for both P1 and P2. However, it is difficult to find
53 conclusive results about the preferable nominal thickness, as the curves are quite flat; then, at point P1

1 we could appreciate that the smallest gyradii with convex lenses are in the interval between 15 and 25
 2 voxels, but in the rest of the cases we just can affirm that this interval is not worst than any other
 3 Finally, if we compare these data with those found for the underwater case, we can appreciate
 4 that the transcranial aberrated corrected beam is slightly bigger indicating that the dispersion of the
 5 energy in the skull is not absolutely compensated by the lens. This effect is particularly appreciable in
 6 the transverse gyradius at point P3.
 7

8
 9 **Figure 5.** Focusing quality indicators calculated by transcranial simulation with 760 kHz at points P1,
 10 P2 and P3, for concave (fast) and convex (slow) lenses. Indicators are: (a) Longitudinal and (b)
 11 transverse deviation, (c) transverse and (d) total gyradius, (e) beam volume, (f) orientation and (g)
 12 energetic overlapping.
 13

14 **Focal volume:** In brief, we can summarize that the results found for the focal volume are in great
 15 accordance with that of gyradius (Figure 5e). So, convex and concave lenses present similar results
 16 between them, and the trends found in underwater and transcranial cases are also very similar. What
 17 can be highlighted is that the aberrated corrected beams are notably bigger that those found in the
 18 underwater case. This difference could seem excessive if compared with that found at radii but this
 19 apparent incoherence is associated with (i) the different units of gyradius and volume so the relative
 20 uncertainties in volume are three times bigger than those of gyradius, and additionally (ii) the central
 21 part of the beam is reasonably similar between transcranial and underwater cases, but as we separate

1 from the target point there is more diffuse energy in the transcranial case, and an important fraction of
 2 this diffuse energy exceeds the arbitrary threshold of -6dB. Finally the interval of lens thickness
 3 between 10 and 25 voxels is associated with the best results at P1 and this fact is not in contradiction
 4 with the flat trends found at P2 and P3

5 **Orientation** This indicator, as has been defined, is highly sensitive to small asymmetries or
 6 irregularities associated to a non exact aberration correction. Therefore we can see trends much more
 7 abrupt than in other evaluated indicators (Figure 5(f)). With the exception of point P3, with optimum
 8 values at the range between 10 and 25 voxels, there is not a clear interval of preferred nominal
 9 thicknesses, but at least we find again that the worst values are at the extremes of the curves, what is
 10 somehow coherent with the rest of the evaluation. No clear preferences are obtained between concave
 11 and convex lenses, or between further and closer points.

12
 13 **Energetic overlapping:** The values of this indicator are deeply linked to the values of previously
 14 commented ones, and therefore data at Figure 5(g) summarises what we have seen. Then, in
 15 comparison with overlappings at the underwater case, we find here smaller values and rougher
 16 trends. Particularly at point P3 we obtain the worst focusing in transcranial whereas was the best
 17 focused in water, being this great reduction of focusing probably related with the irregularity of the
 18 skull region crossed in this case. All the overlappings are between 20% and 45%, and the interval of
 19 nominal thickness in which these values are largest is again between 10 and 25 voxels for both
 20 concave and convex lenses at the three points evaluated. Finally, the values obtained for this indicator
 21 in transcranial simulations seem to be notably independent on the type of lens or the target distance.
 22

23 **Figure 6.** Focusing quality indicators calculated by simulation in water with 380 kHz, at points P1, and
 24 P2, for concave (fast) and convex (slow) lenses. Indicators are: (a) Longitudinal deviation, (b)
 25 transverse gyradius, (c) beam volume and (d) energetic overlapping.

26
 27
 28
 29 **4.3. Emission in water at 380 kHz**

30
 31 Since the results found are very similar to those seen at 760kHz, the analysis of the graphical
 32 information shown in Figure 6 is here faced as a whole. Thus, we can point out that, in the case of
 33 concave lenses, all the parameters in both points show the same type of trend, consisting of a

1 worsening of the indicator quality as the thickness of the lens increases. This is not contradictory with
 2 what was seen in the evaluation at 760kHz, but is due to the fact that the smallest possible lens
 3 thickness -conditioned to the value of the water wavelength in the concave lenses- is greater than the
 4 values that define the optimum interval. In the case of convex lenses, whose thickness is not limited a
 5 priori, two types of trend are shown in the indicators and one exception. One type of trend,
 6 appreciated at beam volume and at both gyradii, is simply flat, so that no conclusion can be drawn
 7 from it. For the rest of the indicators, and for both points, the same trend seen for the previous
 8 frequency is observed, that is, we find an area of optimum values between 10 and 30 voxels thick.
 9 Although this trend is slight in several indicators, it is clearer for overlapping, which is the most
 10 relevant indicator. Finally, it is worth mentioning that (i) in the transverse deviation no significant
 11 trend is observed, since its values in the underwater case are only indicative of the numerical error
 12 and that (ii) in the longitudinal deviation no clear optimum is appreciated, but we interpret that the
 13 indicator improves the smaller the thickness of the lens. This last result could be justified by the fact
 14 that the thickness of the lens conditions the position of the transducer to maintain the position of the
 15 phase registration curve. Therefore, it seems logical that the change of position of the transducer in the
 16 longitudinal axis affects the longitudinal position of the focus, so that this indicator is the only one in
 17 which the results indicate that it is preferable to reduce the thickness as much as possible.
 18
 19

20
 21 **Figure 7.** Focusing quality indicators calculated by transcranial simulation with 380 kHz at points P1
 22 and P2, for concave (fast) and convex (slow) lenses. Indicators are: (a) Longitudinal and (b) transverse
 23 deviation, (c) transverse gyradius, (d) beam volume and (e) energetic overlapping.
 24

25 *4.4. Transcranial emission at 380 kHz*
 26

27 The results found (Figure 7) are very similar to those of the underwater case at the same
 28 frequency, although the transverse deviation, which is not a significant indicator in the underwater
 29 case, broadly shows the same trend seen in the rest of the parameters. That is, an area of optimum
 30 values between 10 and 30 voxels for convex lenses, while in concave lenses, which do not cover this
 31 range, the indicator worsens as the thickness increases. It is also worth noting the high parallelism of

1 the results found in both underwater and transcranial cases, which can be justified because the
 2 capacity of the skull to generate aberrations is lower in the case of a larger wavelength
 3

4 4.5. Experimental validation

5
 6 The results of the field measurements are summarized in Figure 8. First, the measured field and
 7 the corresponding simulation at 1.12 MHz along the axis of symmetry of the lens are shown in Fig.
 8 8(a). A good agreement is found between the simulation and the experiment. The focal spot is well
 9 described by simulations. Note that the focal spot peaks at $z = 28.3$ mm instead at $z = F = 30$ mm. This
 10 is due to the diffraction effects of the wavefront, in accordance with the axial-focal shift expected in
 11 any focused source as described in [47]. The pressure distribution was measured in the sagittal plane,
 12 $p(x, z)$, and the normalized absolute value of the field is shown in Fig.8(b) for the experiment and
 13 Fig.8(c) for the simulation. An excellent agreement is found between both fields. Remark that the field
 14 shows excellent symmetry as expected by the geometry of the lens. The corresponding transverse field
 15 distribution measured at the focal spot is shown in Figs. 8(d-f) for both, simulation and experiment.
 16 The focal spot presents a sharp transverse size smaller than the wavelength (about 1.2 mm). Although
 17 small discrepancies are observed at the side-lobes of the pattern, the sharp focus observed
 18 experimentally agrees well with simulations, showing that the proposed computational method
 19 describe in an accurate manner the expected behavior of the holographic lenses.

20
 21 **Figure 8.** Results of the experimental validation test. (a) Experimental (red markers) and simulated
 22 (black continuous) normalized pressure field distribution measured at the axis of symmetry. Pressure
 23 field distribution in the sagittal plane, $p(x, z)$, obtained (b) experimentally and (c) numerically. (d)
 24 Experimental (red markers) and simulated (black continuous) normalized pressure field distribution
 25 in the transverse direction x measured at the focal spot. Corresponding pressure distributions in the
 26 transverse plane, $p(x, y)$, obtained (e) experimentally and (f) numerically.

30 5. Discussion

1
2 Although the extension of this study does not allow the quantification of the statistical
3 significance of the results obtained, certain relevant evidences can be extracted, which are discussed
4 below. In order to obtain a conclusive result regarding the precise physical parameters that define the
5 optimum lens, it would be necessary -in addition to more similar experiments to increase the
6 statistical significance of the results- also to increase the number of types of simulations, with more
7 wavelength values, more distances to the focus point (including points beyond the geometric centre of
8 the transducer) or more lens apertures. Various numerical methods should also be applied, as the
9 wave speed directly affects the stability of the calculation which limits the reliability of the results for
10 lenses with speeds highly different to the medium, whether faster or slower.

11 However, although we cannot determine the exact properties of the optimal lens, the presence of
12 a trend that allows the establishment of an interval of desirable values has been clearly evidenced by
13 the results obtained. Indeed, as seen in Figures 4 to 7, all the quantitative focusing indicators obtained
14 in the simulations with 760kHz, for the two types of lens, at any point and with or without skull,
15 present a behaviour regarding the lens thickness that can be expressed as follows. For thicknesses
16 greater than a certain value of about 15 or 20 voxels the indicators worsen with the increase in
17 thickness, although this relationship is moderate and sometimes even flat (as in the case of the
18 transcranial focal volume in point 2). For thicknesses smaller than 10 or 15 voxels the dependence
19 between the value of the indicators and the thickness is much more abrupt, so that thicknesses under
20 10 voxels are clearly discouraged. This trend is manifested in all indicators in the case of slow lenses,
21 since with fast lenses thicknesses smaller than water wavelength cannot be obtained, however, this
22 result could not be conclusive because the bad value of indicators could be partially associated with
23 the numerical error in the propagation inside the lens, given that the number of points per wavelength
24 in extremely thin lenses is less than recommended [32]. In any case, and due to the fact that the
25 impedance value has been fixed to achieve total transparency, which means that there are no internal
26 reflections in the lens, we can assume that the possible numerical error in the phase associated with a
27 path inside the lens as short as 5 or 10 voxels would not have a considerable cumulative effect, but
28 that the origin of the error is precisely the strong discretization of the values of the phase at the exit of
29 the lens associated with the fact that its thickness is defined by such scarce number of voxels. This
30 hypothesis is reinforced by the fact that in the range of 10 to 15 voxels we can already see, albeit in a
31 moderate way, that lower thickness implies worse value of the indicators.

32 Similar conclusions can be drawn from the analysis of the results obtained with the 380kHz
33 emission. Fast lenses here are always thicker than the optimum, so it is observed that greater
34 thicknesses directly imply worse indicators; as for slow lenses, we observe the trend commented in
35 the case of 760Hz with all indicators, with the sole exception of the longitudinal deviation.

36 In the simulations at both frequencies certain additional relationships can be seen, which are
37 briefly discussed below. Thus, as point P1 is farther away than P2, higher values of focus size or
38 gyradius are obtained, which is predictable; however obtained values of the transverse deviation or
39 the transcranial energetic overlapping are similar at both evaluated points. In water simulations,
40 however, it seems clear that the indicators are better for the farthest point, which makes sense since a
41 farther target implies smoother lens curvatures which results in (i) the appearance of fewer edges
42 associated with the phase shift 2π ; and, on the one hand and, (ii) a smaller deviation of rays at the
43 boundary of the lens, which is better suited to the thin lens model and additionally activates less
44 energy in form of s-waves. Another foreseeable result is that in the process of passing through the
45 skull, even if the incidence is made with phase correction, energy is dispersed, so that the beam
46 contours are diffuse and indicators obtained are generally worse than that of underwater case.

47 The simulation with several frequencies -one of which deviates from the usual values in medical
48 treatments- aims to study whether the optimal thickness values are intrinsic or dependent on the
49 wavelength, given a voxel size. It is observed that with different wavelengths the curves are not
50 displaced in the axis of thicknesses, but that, for both 380kHz and 760kHz, the best indicators are in
51 the zone between 10 and 25 voxels thick, regardless the kind of lens, the distance transducer-target, or
52 the presence or absence of skull. This result deserves to be highlighted by its relevance in order to
53 generalize the study, as all the magnitudes measured in meters of the problem are related. Therefore,
54 if, for instance, the lens aperture, its radius, the transducer-target distance and the wavelength were

1 duplicated simultaneously, then we would have a mathematically equivalent situation to the initial
 2 state (disregarding the effect of absorption) but with a voxel of half the size. If we change only some of
 3 those lengths, we are facing different cases. With that said, finding that the ideal range of thickness (in
 4 voxel) does not depend on either frequency or wavelength is a remarkable result. In this same sense, it
 5 is worth mentioning that the frequencies used in medical treatments (about 1MHz) are associated with
 6 an optimal lens thickness that can be achieved with polymers of fairly common properties, both in the
 7 case of concave and convex lenses, as can be seen in the Tables 1 and 2. On the other hand, in the case
 8 of 380kHz, not usual in transcranial FUS, it can be seen (Table 2) that no material has the necessary
 9 rigidity to reach the concave lenses optimum thickness since fast lenses have a nominal thickness
 10 larger than the wavelength of the sound in the water. This could be solved with slow lenses whose
 11 thickness is not limited, although, as will be seen below, slow lenses are affected by other
 12 inconveniences.

13 The error associated with the possible difference between the speed of the printed lens and the
 14 one assumed in the simulation -represented in the analytical curves of the Figure 3- has not been
 15 evaluated by the set of simulations. This error presents a notable asymmetry, so that it tends
 16 asymptotically to zero on the side of fast lenses, whereas on the side of slow lenses (elastomers) both
 17 this error and that related to discretization tend to not negligible values. Thus, from the point of view
 18 of the focusing quality, we could conclude that lenses "as slow as possible" are discouraged a priori
 19 while lenses "as fast as possible" are recommended as long as they have an adequate impedance, as
 20 will be discussed below.

21
 22 **Figure 9.** Pressure field distribution in the sagittal plane, $p(x, z)$, obtained numerically from two lenses
 23 generated from a particular registered pattern: (a) convex lens made of fluorinated ethylene propylene
 24 and (b) concave lens made of polylactic acid.
 25

26 New evidence in favour of rigid lenses can be drawn from the preliminary results of the
 27 experimental validation (Figure 9); its analytical basis is now discussed. Most of the energy is
 28 propagated in the form of p-waves, however, s-waves cannot be neglected due to the abrupt curvature
 29 often presented by the lenses. Thus, the fact that the s-wave speed is always lower than the p-wave
 30 speed affects each type of lens very differently. In slow lenses, the s-wave speed is even slower which
 31 makes the s-waves even more refractive, allowing the generation of secondary foci between the
 32 primary and the lens; these foci, by geometric proximity to the source, could eventually concentrate
 33 high energy which is undesirable. In fast lenses, on the other hand, the value of the s-wave speed can
 34 be faster than the sound speed at water but also slower. In the first case, the refraction would be lower
 35 than in p-waves so that -if a secondary focus were produced- it would be beyond the primary focus
 36 accumulating low energy; in the second case (s-wave speed lower than water) the s-wave would
 37 present an opposite vergence to the p-wave, so the lens would disperse the energy instead of

concentrating it. Both possibilities in fast lenses are clearly favourable with respect to the risks associated with the application of slow lenses. However, if these are made with elastomers with a Poisson's ratio very close to 0.5, the medium behaviour is practically equivalent to a fluid with a single associated propagation speed, which would somehow validate the use of slow lenses.

The set of simulations aimed to find the range of preferred thicknesses accounting exclusively the effect of the polymer wave speeds. However, the important effect of the impedance must be highlighted and it is discussed briefly here. From the theoretical point of view, it is simple to establish that its preferred value is equal to that of water, but in practice this cannot always be achieved. In fact the velocity of the p-waves, c_p , and the acoustic impedance, z , are related according to the expression $z = \rho_o c_p$ where ρ_o is density. Thus, as shown at Table 1, whereas in fast materials the density is practically constant so that an increase of the speed carries implicitly an increase in the impedance; in the slow ones one can find different densities and therefore water normalised acoustic impedances close to the unit. Highest transparencies nearing 100% are found with fluorocarbons, such the fluorinated ethylene propylene (FEP). Therefore, from the point of view of energy efficiency, it would be preferable a priori to use slow lenses as long as they are elastomers with unitary water normalised impedances. However, from a strictly focusing-quality point of view, the use of fast lenses is still recommended because, as stated in previous sections about sources of error, by knowing the physical properties of the transducer and backing, the phase error associated with internal reflections in the lens can be corrected completely. In any case, although the phase error associated with impedance is known and can be corrected -by designing the lens using Fabry Perot's hypothesis [9]- the fact that total transparency is only reached when impedances of lenses and water are equal constitutes a clear handicap for rigid lenses.

An additional aspect to keep in mind is that the transmission from the transducer to the supposedly spherical inner surface of the lens will be notably affected by the fact that 3D printing does not produce a perfect curve but a voxelated Cartesian model. Thus, the contact between the transducer and the lens is not homogeneous but concentrations of stresses may occur in certain specific vertexes of the lens with the risk of high transmission irregularities. These concentrations will be more pronounced in rigid and crystalline plastics than in deformable and amorphous plastics such as elastomers. Although high impedance gels [48] can soften this effect, we recommend facing its quantitative study in later works. These arguments are no longer valid when emitting by flat transducers, as in the validation experiment.

The choice of a nominal lens thickness associated with a phase shift 2π , not discussed in previous sections, can be justified attending to the results of the simulations. Indeed, they are coincident with the thin lens hypothesis assumed, since -disregarding the error associated with the spatial discretization of the lens- the finer the lens the better the focusing. Therefore, even when Fresnel lenses with a 2π phase shift have many areas of abrupt curvature; their use is reasonably justified compared to continuous lenses or lenses with a larger associated phase shift that would be much thicker.

		Experiment	Simulation		
Frequency /kHz		1112	760	380	
	n_d	15	15	15	28
	d / mm	3,66	3,66	3,66	6,84
	d / λ	2,74	1,87	0,94	1,75
Fast lens	$c_{relative}$	1,57	2,14	---	2,33
	$c / (\text{m/s})$	2340	3180	---	3470
Slow lens	$c_{relative}$	0,73	0,65	0,48	0,64
	$c / (\text{m/s})$	1090	970	720	940

Assumed data

$c_{water} = 1485 \text{m/s}$

voxel size $dh = 0.244 \text{mm}$

Applied equation

$$C_{LENS} = \frac{c_{H_2O}}{1 \pm \frac{c_{H_2O}}{f \cdot n_d \cdot dh}}$$

Table 2. Recommended p-wave speeds and nominal lens thicknesses, d , for the experiment and simulation frequencies, assuming that the number of voxels associated with the ideal nominal thickness value, n_d , is 15. Last column show the minimal value of n_d that can be achieved by the fastest polymer listed in Table 1.

1 Summarizing, we could say that slow lenses have the advantages of (i) certain independence
2 between p-wave speed and acoustic impedance so that it is possible to achieve simultaneously speeds
3 very different to water with very similar impedances and therefore high transparency; and, (ii) in the
4 case of lenses made of elastomers to be used with spherical transducers, an easier mechanical coupling
5 that avoids concentrations of tensions in the micro-vertices of the Cartesian mesh. Fast lenses, on the
6 other hand, have the advantage of (i) a lower risk of energy concentrations in secondary foci
7 associated with s-waves, as well as (ii) a much less vulnerable behaviour related to possible
8 inaccuracies in the manufacturing processes of the lens. Finally, it should be noted that results of
9 simulations indicate that the range of optimum lens thicknesses given a 3D printer voxel size is
10 coincident for both fast and slow lenses, and notably independent of other factors such as emission
11 frequency, transducer aperture, or transducer-target distance.

14 6. Conclusions

16 In this work we have looked for the best polymers to 3D print holographic acoustic lenses, in
17 particular to be applied in the correction of transcranial FUS aberrations. Therefore, although there are
18 many parameters affecting the focusing quality of a lens, some of them affect in a trivial way, being
19 simple to establish a priori the desirable value. We can, for example, establish as desirable that the
20 material must be homogeneous and with low acoustic absorption. However, there are two main
21 parameters with a non-trivial relationship with quality: the impedance and the p-wave speed in the
22 lens material. As for the impedance, and attending to focusing quality, any value can be optimal if we
23 know exactly the properties of medium, transducer and backing. Since their exact values are difficult
24 to know, it is as much as saying that not all impedances values are optimal, and the only robust value
25 that does not require the exact knowledge of all agents, is an acoustic impedance equal to that of
26 water.

27 Thus, this study is centered on the effect of the sound speed of the polymer, highly related to the
28 thickness of the lens. Particularly this work proves that there is an optimum range of lens thicknesses,
29 given that analytical models work best for fine lenses, but the discretization in voxels associated with
30 3D printing is a greater source of error the finer the lens. The set of numerical and experimental
31 evaluations leaves a series of clear evidences. If we divide the materials into three groups of p-wave
32 speeds, such as (i) notably lower than water (ii) near water, and (iii) notably higher than water, it
33 becomes clear, both from theoretical analyses and simulations, that the second group should be
34 avoided. On the other hand, attending to numerical simulations, optimal lens thicknesses are in the
35 same range, between 10 and 25 voxels, for both slow and fast lenses, although fast lenses have certain
36 advantages.

37 The main advantages associated with fast lenses are the following: (i) in fast lenses the presence
38 of s-waves contaminates the main focus in a less risky way than in slow lenses, (ii) its behaviour is
39 much more robust against eventual manufacturing errors that result in lenses with a p-wave speed
40 different than expected, and (iii) rigid crystalline polymers employed for fast lenses have smaller
41 acoustic absorptions than more deformable amorphous thermoplastics. Slow lenses, especially if they
42 are made of elastomers in which the formation of waves can be neglected, have a higher energy
43 efficiency associated with the value of their impedances, but do not offer clear advantages if the
44 focusing quality is strictly evaluated.

45 Transcranial aberration correction based on 3D printed lenses was proposed last year as a
46 technology capable of competing with the currently established solution based on phased arrays. The
47 advantages of the 3D lenses are fundamentally related to the lower initial acquisition cost of the
48 equipment, whereas the phased arrays can be straighter forward in their later use. However, apart
49 from practical criteria of ease or cost, scientific criteria regarding the focusing accuracy must be
50 considered when choosing one of these alternatives. In future works we will deal with the exhaustive
51 comparison between focusing quality achieved by 3D lenses and phased arrays; so the present study
52 was proposed as a necessary step prior to such a comparison between both technologies.

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15
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